

DEVELOPING TEACHING PROCEDURE OF LISTENING COMPREHENSION THROUGH METACOGNITIVE STRATEGY

Nurhafni Siregar,

Reni Sapitriⁱ

Universitas Muslim Nusantara Al-Washliyah,
Indonesia

Abstract:

In the context of education at the elementary, secondary and tertiary level, communicative competence in English has a function as a tool for accessing information, fostering interpersonal relationships, and exchanging information. Listening activities have a portion of 45% of communication skills, which is also the basis for the acquisition of foreign languages which includes all three other language skills (speaking, reading, and writing). However, so far there has been a gap between expectations and reality in learning listening courses in higher education, especially in the UMN Al-Wasliyah English Language Education Study Program. In accordance with the observations of researchers as teaching staff in the UMN Al-Wasliyah English Language Education Study Program, there are still many students who do not have adequate knowledge and skills in listening courses. The purpose of this study is to realize the learning process of listening courses that can improve students' thinking through metacognitive strategies. The results of this development are useful to improve the quality of the process and student achievement and also have a strategic function in the learning process, which can increase students' confidence, responsibility, and motivation. The research subjects were students of the English Language Education study program UMN Al-Wasliyah in the fourth semester of the 2018/2019 academic year as many as 30 people. Data collection techniques that will be used are questionnaires, document surveys, interviews, observations, and tests.

Keywords: developing, teaching procedure, listening, metacognitive strategy

1. Introduction

In the context of education at the elementary, secondary and tertiary level, communicative competence in English has a function as a tool for accessing information,

ⁱ Correspondence: email nurhafni.siregar@umnaw.ac.id, renisafitriharahap@gmail.com

fostering interpersonal relationships, and exchanging information. The listening activity has a portion of 45% of communication skills, which is also the basis for the acquisition of foreign languages which includes all three other language skills (speaking, reading, and writing) (Feyten, 1991). Thus, it is necessary to improve the quality of the learning process that can improve student learning achievement in listening courses as expected. However, so far there has been a gap between expectations and reality in learning listening courses in higher education, especially in the UMN Al-Wasliyah English Language Education Study Program. In accordance with the observations of researchers as teaching staff in the UMN Al-Wasliyah English Language Education Study Program, there are still many students who do not have adequate knowledge and skills in listening courses.

Based on the IELTS listening value in September 2018, 75 students for listening courses tested at the beginning of the semester seven of the Academic Year 2017/2018 are still in the low category, which is below the band 5. Predicted causes of low student achievement listening subjects are learning models, materials teaching, syllabus, lesson plan, and evaluation tools that have been used so far have not supported the learning process of innovative, interactive listening courses that are able to improve students' thinking processes. To realize the learning process of listening courses that are able to improve the thinking process of students, learning models based on metacognitive strategies need to be developed. The results of this development are useful to improve the quality of the process and student learning achievements and also have a strategic function in the learning process, which can increase students' confidence, responsibility, and motivation (Rahimirad and Zaree-ee (2015), Hariri (2014), Mansoor and Ebrahim, (2014), Tabeei, Tarmizi and Ahmadi (2013), and Birjandi (2012).

The learning model is learning based on metacognitive strategies, namely a level in the thought process to control the mind and regulate the way of learning (Vandergrift and Goh, 2012). In other words, metacognitive is the awareness of thinking about what is known and what is unknown. In the context of learning, students know how to learn, know the abilities and modalities of learning possessed, and know the best learning strategies for effective learning (Baker, 2002; Wender, 1998). Through this research and development it is expected to produce product specifications in the form of the realization of listening learning models that have the characteristics of metacognitive strategies that can build learning independence by making students aware of broadly and linking things that are already known to what is planned (planning). Then monitor what is being done by linking between planned components (monitoring). Finally, assess the effectiveness and feasibility of the model developed. The final product to be produced is a learning model of listening courses based on metacognitive strategies in the form of technical implementation of the model.

To realize the learning process of listening courses that are able to improve the thinking process of students, learning models based on metacognitive strategies need to be developed. The results of this development are useful to improve the quality of the process and student learning achievements and also have a strategic function in the

learning process, which can increase students' confidence, responsibility, and motivation (Rahimirad and Zaree-ee (2015), Hariri (2014), Mansoor and Ebrahim, (2014), Tabeii, Tarmizi and Ahmadi (2013), and Birjandi (2012)). The learning model is learning based on metacognitive strategies, namely a level in the thought process to control the mind and regulate the way of learning (Vandergrift and Goh, 2012). In other words, metacognitive is the awareness of thinking about what is known and what is unknown. In the context of learning, students know how to learn, know the abilities and modalities of learning possessed, and know the best learning strategies for effective learning (Baker, 2002; Wender, 1998).

Based on the explanation above, the researchers felt interested in conducting research on the development of learning models of appropriate and effective listening courses through validation from experts and practitioners. The development research is the learning model of listening comprehension II courses at universities that have the characteristics of metacognitive strategies. In particular, the purpose of this development research is to reveal the process of developing a learning model based on metacognition strategies that are appropriate to the learning needs of listening at UMN Al-Wasliyah.

2. Research Problem

Based on the background of the research problem, the problems of the research are formulated as follows:

- 1) What is the objective condition of the implementation of the learning strategy of current listening comprehension in the UMN Al-Wasliyah English Education Study Program?
- 2) How is the development of practical and effective comprehension listening learning models using metacognitive strategies?

2.1 Significant of the Study

Based on the description previously stated on the background of the research problem, the purpose of this study is to reveal:

- 1) objective conditions for implementing learning strategies for listening comprehension at the UMN Al-Wasliyah Educational Study Program;
- 2) validity, practicality and effectiveness of developing listening comprehension learning models using metacognitive strategies.

3. Literature Review

Metacognition in learning was originally formulated by several experts decades ago. James (1890), a philosopher uses the term reflective thinking with his idea, "*the stream of thought*" (Goodman, 2013). Then, Vigotsky (1934) a Russian psychologist used the term cognitive development (in McLeod, 2014). Although these experts do not use the term metacognition, the concept of metacognition has received attention.

At present the concept of metacognition in the science of education and language learning still rests on the concept of Flavel (1976). He explained that, metacognition is, *"One's knowledge regarding cognitive processes and products related to them refers to metacognition, among other things, to active monitoring and consequent regulation and orchestration of these processes in relation to these cognitive objects or data on which they bear, usually in the service of some concrete goals or objectives"*. (An and Shi, 2013).

In this definition, metacognition is generally seen as one's knowledge of the process of its own cognition and the results it has regarding it. Among other things, metacognition refers to active supervision of the cognitive processes and regulations that follow them and the unification of these processes that are related to the objects or data that is passed, usually to achieve a real goal. In connection with the concept of learning, Flavel (1979) defines metacognition as, *"be aware of one's own cognitive processes and everything else that is relevant to information related to the learning process"* (in Movahed, 2014). Can be defined that, metacognition is the awareness of students about the process and results of thinking in the learning process. Another definition of metacognition is *"learners' automatic awareness of their own knowledge and their ability to understand, control, and manipulate their own cognitive processes"* (Hariri, 2014). Metacognition is the automatic awareness of students of their knowledge and ability to understand, control, and manipulate cognitive processes.

From all of these opinions there is one common understanding that metacognitive strategies in learning comprehension are the steps of learning that involve high-level thinking processes that are able to increase awareness of the process of comprehension listening.

Vandergrift and Goh (2012) suggested that the listening comprehension learning model based on metacognitive strategies has 5 steps that can be applied in learning activities, namely;

- 1) pre-listening / prediction stage;
- 2) first listen / first verification stage;
- 3) second listen / second verification stage;
- 4) third listen / final verification stage;
- 5) reflection / goal setting.

In learning listening, metacognitive strategy has the characteristics namely the learning process that is directed at improving planning skills, monitoring (monitoring), and evaluating (evaluation). Students know how to learn, know the abilities and modalities of learning possessed, and know the best learning strategies for effective learning. Thus, the target of this development research is to improve (1) the quality of the learning comprehension course, and (2) produce development products in the form of lecturers' manuals on learning comprehension models using metacognitive strategies, student workbooks.

4. Research Methodology

A. Developing Model

Research and development are the research method used to produce a product and to test the effectiveness of the product (Sugiyono, 2013: 297). In educational context, Borg and Gall (1983: 772) also stated that educational research and development (R&D) is a process used to develop and validate educational products. The steps of this process usually referred to as R&D cycle, which consists of studying research finding pertinent to the product to be developed, developing the products based on the findings, field testing it in the setting where it will be used eventually, and revising it to correct the deficiencies found in the field of testing stage. In more rigorous programs of R&D, this cycle is repeated until the field-test data indicate that the product meets its behaviorally defined objectives.

The research and development model used in this research was Borg and Gall model. The chosen model was taken because of these scientific reasons: 1) this model has systematic procedures therefore the researchers do not need typical adaptation, 2) this model is considered applicable to the developing model of teaching procedures of listening comprehension which meets the needs of higher education.

B. The Procedures of Developing Model

The procedures or the stages of R&D was Borg and Gall (1989) which was quoted by Putra (2012: 119-121) which consists of 10 stages. But in this research, nine stages was conducted as follows;

Picture 3.1: Scheme of the Procedures of Developing Model by Borg and Gall

C. The Subject of the Treatment

The subject of the treatment needed to observe the events, object, behavioural of the key person which is represented the actual fact, data, and necessary information (Satori and Komariah, 2013: 262). This research is conducted at Universitas Muslim Nusantara Al Washiyah Medan Indonesia. The subjects was the students of English education department which consists of 30 students, 3 lecturers of listening comprehension.

D. Instruments in Collecting the Data

The instruments administered in collecting the data was interview, questionnaires, observation sheets and test.

- interview: semistandardized interview was used in this stage which has purposes to find the problem from the interviewee. The result of this interview helps the researchers to map the students' background and the obstacles in the field related to the teaching listening comprehension.
- questionnaires: the questionnaires collect the data of need analysis, the validity of the developed product and to see the effectivity of the developed teaching procedures model.
- observation sheets: the observation was done to observe the implementation metacognitive strategy in each treatment in the field.
- test: listening comprehension was measured based on the indicators in each product designing stages. This test measures the effectivity of the teaching procedures implementation.

E. Technique of Analyzing the Data

Data analysis was done after collecting the result of all instruments such as interview, questionnaires, observation sheet and test.

- interview: the collecting data was analyzed by using qualitative analysis which consists of data reduction, displaying the data and verification. As Miles and Huberman (1984) stated that in order to get well interpretation of the data, it emphasizes the researchers to have high quality of thinking, creativity and patient.
- questionnaires: descriptive analysis and quantitative statistic analysis was used and each criteria displayed on percentage.
- observation: quantitative statistical analysis was used to describe the criteria of the observation sheet displayed on percentage.
- test: descriptive and inferential analysis was done to interpretate the result of the test.

5. Result & Discussion

This research and development of metacognitive strategy in teaching listening comprehension was conducted in four months through five stages, they are; (1) preliminary investigation, (2) design, (3) realization/construction, (4) test, evaluation, and revision and (5) implementation. This chapter reveals the data and data analysis in the form of (1) developing metacognitive strategy based on the original model, then developed through designing, construction, evaluation and revision, and implementation stages, (2) evaluation of the effectiveness of the teaching procedures model in teaching listening comprehension at English education department of UMN Al Washliyah Medan.

Figure 3.1: Design of Developed Teaching Procedures of Listening Comprehension

The following is the final finding of this research; these are the crucial development of the teaching model of metacognitive strategy.

Table 3.3: The complete stages of metacognitive teaching procedure developed model

Original MSM	Developed MSM
Stage 1. Pre-listening/prediction	Stage 1. Introduction
Stage 2. First listen/first verification	Stage 2. Pre-listening/prediction
Stage 3. Second listen/second verification	Stage 3. First listen/first verification
Stage 4. Third listen/final verification	Stage 4. Second listen/second verification
Stage 5. Final reflection	Stage 5. Third listen/final verification
	Stage 6. Final reflection
	Stage 7. Self Report and Process-Based Discussion

6. Conclusion

This developed model of teaching procedures of listening comprehension through metacognitive strategy is one of the best solutions to solve the problem in the area of teaching listening comprehension. Therefore, this product emphasizes the lecturers and the students to implement this strategy in their listening classes.

However, it is suggested for the lecturers or teachers to modify this model according to the students' need and background.

Acknowledgement

The author would like to thank the Rector of the Universitas Muslim Nusantara Al Washliyah (UMN Al Washliyah) through the Chairperson of LP2M UMN Al Washliyah, who has supported especially by providing financial assistance as part of carrying out focal activities of Tri Dharma in Higher Education, one of which is by conducting research, so that the outcome of the research can be eventually published in a journal.

References

- Arikunto, Suharsimi (2005). *Dasar-Dasar Evaluasi Pendidikan* (Edisi Revisi). Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Baker, L. (2002). Metacognition in comprehension instruction. In C. Block & M. Pressley (Eds.), *Comprehension instruction: Research-based best practices* (pp. 77–95). New York: Guilford Press.
- Beran, M. J., Brandl, J. L., Perner, J., dan Proust, J. (2012). *Foundation of Metacognition*. Oxford: University Press.
- Berg, Bruce, L. (2007). *Qualitative Research Method for the Social Science: An Introduction to Theory and Methods*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon, Inc.
- Brown, A. L., Bransford, J. D., Ferrara, R. A., & Campione, J. C. (1983). *Learning, Remembering, and Understanding*. In *handbook of child psychology* (pp. 77-166). New York: Wiley.
- Cauldwell, Richard T. (1998). Faith, Hope, and Charity: The Vices of Listening Comprehension. *The Language Teacher Online*, 22(7).
- Cubukcu, F. (2008). Enhancing Vocabulary Development and Reading Comprehension through Metacognitive Strategies. *Issues in Educational Research*, 18 (1).
- Depdikbud (1995). *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia*. Jakarta: Balai Pustaka.
- Dick, W. Carey, L. & Carey, J. O. (2005). *The Systematic Design of Instruction*. Illonis, Glenview: Scott, Foersman and Company.
- Dunkel, P. (1986). Developing listening fluency in L2: Theoretical principles and pedagogical considerations. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70, 99–106.
- Feyten, C. M. (1991). The power of listening ability: An overlooked dimension in language acquisition. *The Modern Language Journal*, 75, 173-180.
- Flavell, J. H. (1976). Metacognitive aspects of problem solving. In L. B. Resnick (Ed.), *The nature of intelligence* (pp. 231–235). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Flavell, J. H., P. H. Miller, and S. A. Miller (1993). *Cognitive Development*. 3rd ed. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Garner, R. (1987). *Metacognition and Reading Comprehension*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex Publishing.
- Gilakjani, A. P. dan Ahmadi, M. R. (2011). A Study of Factors Affecting EFL Learners' English Listening Comprehension and the Strategies for Improvement. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, Vol. 2, No. 5, pp. 977-988, (online),

- (<http://www.academypublication.com/issues/past/jltr/vol02/05/05.pdf>) diakses 17 Oktober 2015.
- Hartman, H. J. (2001). *Metacognition and Learning Instruction*. New York: Springer.
- Jacobs, J. E., & Paris, S. G. (1987). Children's metacognition about reading: Issues in definition, measurement, and instruction. *Educational Psychologist*, 22, 255-278.
- Macaro, E., Vanderplank, R., & Graham, S. (2005). *A systematic review of the role of prior knowledge in unidirectional listening comprehension*. London: EPPI-Centre, Social Science Research Unit, Institute of Education, University of London.
- Nation, I. S. P. dan Newton, J. (2009). *Teaching ESL/EFL Listening and Speaking*. New York: Routledge.
- Nation, I. S. P., dan Macalister, J. (2010). *Language Curriculum Design*. New York: Routledge.
- Nord, J. R. (1980). Developing listening fluency before speaking: an alternative paradigm. *System* 8 1: 1-22.
- Rost, M. (1994). *Introduction to Listening*. London: Penguin Group
- Rusman (2012). *Model-Model Pembelajaran: Mengembangkan Profesionalisme Guru*, Jakarta: PT Grafindo Persada.
- Schneider W. (2008). The development of metacognitive knowledge in children and adolescents: Major trends and implications for education. *Mind, Brain and Education*. 2(3):114-121.
- Vandergrift, L. (1999). Facilitating second language listening comprehension: Acquiring successful strategies. *ELT Journal*, 53, 168-176.
- Vandergrift, L., & Tafaghodtari, M. 2010. Teaching L2 Learners How to Listen Does Make a Difference: An Empirical Study. *Language Learning*, 60, 470-467. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9922.2009.00559.x>
- Vandergrift, L. 2003. Orchestrating strategy use: Toward a model of the skilled second language listener. *Language Learning*, 53, 463-496.
- Vandergrift, L. (2004). Listening to Learn or Learning to Listen? *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 24, 3-25

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions, and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of English Language Teaching shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).